

Analysis of tropical nights in Spain (1970–2023): Minimum temperatures as an indicator of climate change

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Abstract

In the current context of climate change, the increase in minimum temperatures recorded in recent decades has received special scientific attention due to its importance for the proper night's sleep and health of the population, among other considerations. One of the main indicators usually considered refers to the frequency of tropical nights ($\geq 20^{\circ}\text{C}$), which have begun to become widespread in regions hitherto excluded from this type of event. This paper analyses tropical nights in Spain between 1970 and 2023, addressing their mean annual occurrence, their intensity, their monthly distribution and the average number of consecutive tropical nights recorded, as well as their relationship with relative humidity. The results, based on the analysis of 75 homogenized series located in 44 different provinces, allow us to differentiate seven large areas based on the minimum temperature in which there has been an increase in the frequency and intensity of tropical nights, which progressively extend the season in which they can appear. Similarly, a generalized increase in the maximum number of consecutive nights thermally above 20°C was identified, in addition to the presence of high relative humidity in coastal areas during these episodes.

KEYWORDS

climate change, minimum temperature, night-time temperature, trends, tropical night

1 | INTRODUCTION

The daily minimum temperature can be defined as the lowest thermal value recorded at a given location during the 24 h that constitute the observation period of each day, a figure that is usually recorded in the hours close to sunrise. The importance of this climate parameter is unquestionable from multiple perspectives, given the variety of areas and aspects that may be affected by possible fluctuations in it—ecosystems, agriculture, human

health, hydrological cycles, etc. This has been evidenced by multiple scientific studies framed in different geographical and climatic contexts (Åström et al., 2015; Dupuis, 2014; Hatfield & Prueger, 2015; Shen et al., 2016).

The international scientific community has repeatedly warned about the considerable increase in minimum temperatures being experienced worldwide, especially in urban areas (IPCC, 2023). Large parts of the globe, such as most of Africa, northern Eurasia and southeast Asia, are experiencing a more notable thermal increase in

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minimums than in maximums (IPCC, 2023), a circumstance that has encouraged the development of research aimed at analysing the impacts of this phenomenon on the health and well-being of the population. In Spain, the most pessimistic predictions suggest that, on average, during the last decade of this century, the minimum temperature could exceed 14°C, more than five degrees above the average recorded between 1950 and 2014 (Figure 1).

Thus, global change is already deteriorating the physical and mental conditions of citizens through a multitude of direct and indirect impacts which magnitude depends on the differential hazard, exposure and vulnerability present in each territory and society (IPCC, 2022) (Figure 2). The health impacts of the phenomenon are widely documented; works such as that of Minor et al. (2022) have shown that the duration of human sleep—and thus individual rest—decreases as the minimum night-time temperature increases above a certain threshold. Laaidi et al. (2011), on the other hand, based on data related to the heat wave that hit much of Europe in August 2003, showed that continuous exposure of the elderly to high minimum temperatures increases the probability of death during hot episodes, at least in urban environments. On the other hand, according to these authors, daytime temperature did not exhibit, in this episode, a statistically significant relationship with deaths. Furthermore, Mullins and Corey (2019) link high temperatures and mental health, while there are multiple investigations linking climate change with the emergence—or reappearance—of some pathogens that raise neglected tropical diseases in regions that have so far remained unaffected by such phenomena (Booth, 2018; Caminade et al., 2018; El-Sayed & Kamel, 2020). Thus, the alteration in the patterns of temperature, wind, atmospheric dust and humidity, among others, would be causing a reconfiguration in the incidence of certain viral, bacterial and parasitic diseases (El-Sayed & Kamel, 2020).

These and other consequences of climate change on public health are of international concern, according to reports such as the US National Climate Assessment (Hayden et al., 2023) or the Report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change (Romanello et al., 2023). Strategies and plans for climate adaptation around the world also include evidence and measures aimed at preserving the well-being of citizens in the face of the environmental situation (European Commission, 2021; Government of Canada, 2023; Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare, 2016; MITECO, 2020).

In this context of growing analysis of the health issue in relation to the ongoing environmental change, the study of certain indicators that have an impact on health and public welfare is of special interest. Among them, it is undoubtedly worth mentioning tropical nights

(hereinafter TN), that is, those with temperatures that do not fall below 20°C at any time (Rippstein et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a broad consensus in the field of climatology and bioclimatology on the importance of quantifying and characterizing TN (European Environment Agency, 2020). However, depending on the specific features of the analysed area, the indicated thermal threshold may vary to assess the impact on public health more accurately (Cropper & Cropper, 2016; Ha & Yun, 2012).

This paper analyses the TN phenomenon in Spain, a Mediterranean country with one of the highest levels of climate-related risk in Europe (Eckstein et al., 2021). In addition, its climate presents influences and features that coincide with the environmental characteristics of tropical latitudes in some regions, although it cannot be included within the climatic regimes considered strictly *tropical*, as shown in Figure 3 (Capel-Molina, 1978; Font-Tullot, 1983; Martin-Vide & Olcina, 2001). The Canary archipelago deserves special mention, as its location and conditioning factors are different from those of most of the peninsula and the Balearic Islands (Font-Tullot, 1959).

One of the first attempts to define the TN in the country can be found in the classic work *Climatología de España y Portugal* (Font-Tullot, 1983). Here, the climatological importance of analysing the frequency of hot days and nights, which are considered “oppressive” in terms of individual wellbeing, is confirmed. Although it does not include any reference to the situation in the Canary Islands, it concludes three main ideas in relation to the peninsular situation. First, the area with the highest frequency of TN coincides with the Mediterranean coast, with an annual average of more than 50 nights above 20°C, while the northwestern part of the peninsula is the region with the lowest incidence of these phenomena—at the time of publication of the book, less than one tropical night per year, on average. In the south subplateau and the Ebro Valley, on the other hand, the results were also scarce at that time, with average annual frequencies of less than five and ten TN, respectively. In the Guadalquivir Valley, there were usually no more than 20 nights of this type.

The second conclusion reached refers to the annual distribution of TN. The maximum frequency was concentrated in July and August, while, aside from exceptions such as the Cantabrian coast due to the presence of katabatic winds from the south, the frequency of TN in winter was “practically non-existent” (Font-Tullot, 1983). Finally, it was noted that there were more nights of this type in cities than in less urbanized environments, alluding to the phenomenon of the *urban heat island* (Romero et al., 2006).

Having outlined the main features of TN in most of the country, several scientific studies have been

FIGURE 1 Projected average minimum surface air temperature in Spain (reference period: 1950–2014). Source: World Bank (2021).

FIGURE 2 Pathways from hazards, exposure and vulnerabilities to climate change impacts on health outcomes and health systems. Own elaboration based on IPCC (2023).

FIGURE 3 Geographic location and Köppen–Geiger climate classification of Spain. *Own elaboration based on Beck et al. (2023).*

published in recent decades that have attempted to quantify and characterize the phenomenon (Carvalho et al., 2021; El Kenawy et al., 2011; Lorenzo & Álvarez, 2022; Olcina et al., 2019; Royé & Martí-Ezpeleta, 2015; Sánchez-Lorenzo et al., 2011). The results achieved by these authors reveal some general trends and patterns that can be synthesized into seven main ideas: (1) there is an increase in the frequency of TN in a large part of the country, a trend that has intensified since the 1980s; (2) excluding the Canary Islands, which has scarcely been analysed at an academic level, the Spanish area where TN occur most frequently is represented by the peninsular Mediterranean coast and mainly by the southern half of the country; (3) in general, a greater presence and a more upward trend of TN in the coastal areas is observed; (4) the northernmost third of the peninsula has a less significant incidence of TN than the rest of the country, where the trend is weaker; (5) one of the causes of the increase in TN is due to changes in the zonal atmospheric circulation; (6) an increase in TN is expected in the coming decades and their extension to areas where, until

now, they have been uncommon; and (7) given the importance of TN for the health of the population, urgent adaptation measures are required to cushion the impact of this type of events in areas and societies that are not accustomed to them. Regarding this last idea, authors such as Royé (2017) relate high night-time temperatures to significant increases in the risk of mortality due to natural, respiratory and cardiovascular causes.

Based on all the above, this research complements, broadens and deepens the results and methodologies applied so far for the analysis of TN in Spain. Thus, the most *tropical* of all Spanish regions (the Canary Islands) is included in the analysis. Similarly, the situation of the inland and north of the peninsula is compared to the Mediterranean coast, which has traditionally received more attention in this type of work. A statistical analysis based on updated climatic records is also carried out and, in addition, an effort is made to study the features of TN in greater detail, beyond their annual frequency: intensity, consecutive TN, monthly distribution, relationship with the relative humidity of the air, among others.

2 | DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 | Defining the concept of tropical night

The concept of *tropical night* is widely accepted in the field of climatology to refer to nights that show thermally warm levels. The threshold established to discriminate TN is totally discretionary; the 20°C that, in much of the world, are taken as a reference, are not directly related to the thermal conditions of strictly tropical climates—in the Köppen–Geiger classification, for example, these are distinguished by monthly mean temperatures that, in no case, fall below 18°C (Beck et al., 2005). In this regard, Royé and Martí-Ezpeleta (2015) raise two issues of interest; first, this threshold index is valid in the European context, but is of less use in climatic zones with high minimum temperatures throughout the year, which has led to the aforementioned adoption of other thermal limits in different parts of the world. On the other hand, the authors argue that the mere consideration of the minimum temperature to identify TN may be insufficient, since throughout the night it may exceed 20°C and, in the hours close to sunrise, thermometers may drop below this threshold, masking the fact that a tropical night has actually occurred. Therefore, having hourly data to evaluate the evolution of temperatures throughout the night, and not only at a specific time—the thermal minimum—would be interesting.

Even taking into account this reasoning, in the present work the traditional threshold of 20°C and the minimum daily temperature data, which usually occurs before dawn, are taken as a reference to characterize TN, for reasons related to data availability. Thus, further analysis would require hourly information that is not always available, and, in addition, the selection of the daily minimum makes it possible to compare the results with other previous research and with other places in the world. For this reason, most of the works quoted in the preceding pages, as well as, in general, the most consulted studies on this subject, assume the concept of TN in its classic meaning (20°C), since it allows the general characteristics of the nocturnal temperature regime of a place to be identified in a simple manner and allows for an easy evaluation of possible trends.

In addition to determining the annual frequency of TN in different points of the Spanish geography since 1970, this article describes their intensity—in terms of thermal average, consecutiveness, monthly distribution and relationship with the relative humidity of the air.

2.2 | Area of study and selected stations

This work takes Spain as its spatial framework, 97.5% of which is located on the Iberian Peninsula, the

southwestern tip of Europe, distant from the African continent by about 14 km. The rest of the territory is distributed in two archipelagos—Balearic Islands, in the Mediterranean, and Canary Islands, in the Atlantic facing the western coasts of the Sahara Desert—as well as in two cities located in the north of Africa—Ceuta and Melilla. To determine the fundamental characteristics of TN in the different Spanish climatic regimes since 1970, daily records of minimum temperatures and relative air humidity provided by the State Meteorological Agency (AEMET) were selected from 75 stations—63 in the peninsula and 12 in the Canary and Balearic Islands—located in 44 different provinces, as shown in Figure 4. These series are considered to be representative of the different environmental conditions present in a large part of the national territory and, in addition, they meet optimal conditions for statistical analysis, as can be seen in Figure 5—minimum length of three decades, relative continuity in the records, etc. The complete list of stations can be found in Table S1, Supporting Information.

2.3 | Homogenisation of climate series

Once the stations under analysis were selected, the minimum temperature series were subjected to an exhaustive quality control based on the detection of anomalies exceeding a certain threshold and inhomogeneities in the data. For this purpose, *Climatol* was used, a software widely employed for climate series analysis worldwide given its robustness (Azorín-Molina et al., 2018; Kessabi et al., 2022; Ponce-Cruz et al., 2019; Tudorache et al., 2017). This software, in addition to applying the Standard Normal Homogeneity Test (SNHT) allows gaps in the records to be filled in Guijarro (2023). Figure 6 summarizes how *Climatol* operates, which is based on the iterative execution of procedures.

Regarding homogenisation specifically, as usual, the daily series were not homogenized directly, but rather changes in the mean were first detected on the monthly series and then cut-off points adapted to the available metadata were used to adjust the daily series. The threshold value of inhomogeneity above which the series splits in two—*inht*—has been set at 25. This is the one recommended by the *software* itself since its conservative nature renders it useful for not identifying false jumps in the mean at the expense of missing others of lesser importance. As for the maximum number of nearby data to be used to estimate those of the problem series, up to ten have been used in the first two stages and up to four in the last one. On the other hand, the distance at which the weight of the neighbouring data is worth half has been specified, so that, following the *software* defaults, no weights have been assigned to the data in the first two stages of detection of jumps in the mean

FIGURE 4 Location of selected stations.

FIGURE 5 Number of data in all stations (left) and data availability (right).

and spatial anomalies, while in the third stage—filling in the missing data—the data have been arranged to lose weight with distance, at 100 km, they weigh half.

The procedure described above yields a total of 259 series in which the mean of the Standard normal homogeneity test on anomaly series (SNHT) is 56.45, the

FIGURE 8 Identified clusters based on daily minimum temperature (1970–2023).

The results are grouped in different *clusters* according to the correlation coefficients of the minimum temperatures of each station—the dissimilarity level established as a cut-off value was three. To quantify the temporal changes experienced in each of the indicators and estimate whether the observed trends are significant, the Mann–Kendall trend test, profusely used in Climatology to estimate the trend and its degree of statistical significance (Bartels et al., 2019; Guerreiro et al., 2013; Salmi et al., 2002; Viola et al., 2013), has been applied. By means of this nonparametric test, the statistical significance of the trends was evaluated at $\alpha = 0.01$, $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\alpha = 0.1$, which allowed to quantify the temporal evolution with a confidence level of >99%, >95% and >90%, as shown in the results. On the other hand, the magnitude or rate of temporal change of each indicator has been calculated using the nonparametric Sen's slope procedure, whose validity and academic use have also been proven (Jain et al., 2012; Miró et al., 2009; Ray et al., 2021).

3 | RESULTS

In the following online repository all tables with the complete results of the research are available: https://github.com/resiliex/tropical_nights.

3.1 | Minimum temperatures

From the analysis of the minimum temperature of the stations, a grouping into seven *clusters* or climatic regions is obtained, as shown in Figure 8. As already stated, the grouping into clusters is based on the degree of correlation between the minimum temperatures of the observatories. Then, to facilitate the analysis, each group has been assigned a geographical name according to the majority location of the stations, although there are some cases in which the geographical name given does not correspond to the actual location of the observatory. The most obvious example of this is Badajoz (4452), whose

FIGURE 9 Average daily minimum temperature per cluster and increasing rate (1970–2023).

minimum temperatures are similar to those of the North Inland, despite being located in the southwest of Spain.

The study of the evolution of minimum temperatures confirms that the Canary Islands, due to its geographical location, is a climatic region with thermal values clearly higher than the rest. Thus, in none of the years between 1970 and 2023 has the average daily minimum temperature been below 15°C (Figure 9), a value not yet reached by any other cluster on average, although it has been reached by some stations in the southeast. Along with the Canary Islands, the latter peninsular region also has high minimum temperatures (above 12°C), as well as the Mediterranean and the southwest. On the other hand, the clusters with lower thermal values correspond to the inland and north of the country.

In all stations there is a significant increasing trend with a confidence level of 99% (see table 1 of the repository), although this increase is not homogeneous territorially. The region where the most rapid rise is occurring is the inland, where temperature is increasing by almost 0.4°C per decade. The stations with the highest growth rates are Toledo (0.044°C per year), Ciudad Real (0.043°C) and Getafe (0.043°C). On the contrary, in the Canary Islands the increase is lower than in the rest of the country (0.021°C per year), although this average is conditioned by the results of the Izaña station—within the Teide National

Park, at an altitude of more than 2000 m, where the increase amounts to 0.028°C per year. Thus, in island stations such as those of El Hierro Airport or Santa Cruz de Tenerife, the annual increase is a modest 0.016.

3.2 | Annual frequency and intensity of TN

The annual frequency of TN is higher in the Canary Islands, which averages 92.2 per year, excluding Izaña due to its altitude and different behaviour in relation to the rest of the *cluster* stations. It is followed by the southeast of the Iberian peninsula, with an average of 62.9, the Mediterranean (36) and the southwest (23.9). On the contrary, TN have been, in the last decades, more sporadic events in the inland (about 15 TN per year, on average), in the North Inland (6) and in the Northwest (1), as shown in Figure 10.

The higher frequency of TN in urban environments is very relevant. An example of this is the Community of Madrid, where there are about 30 nights of this type per year in the interior of the city and about nine at Barajas Airport. The latter is less than 15 km from the urban centre, but its surroundings are significantly less urbanized. Other cases of a similar nature are the contrasts between

FIGURE 10 Annual frequency of tropical nights in Spain (1970–2023).

the station located in the city of Albacete (11.4 TN per year) and the one located at the air base, outside the most urbanized perimeter (3.8 TN per year), or the notable difference between the urban observatory of Valencia (73.8) and the airport located in the same province (48.4).

On the other hand, the frequency of TN experienced since 1970 is clearly upward (Figure 11), although the decadal analysis reveals important temporal variations. Despite the fact that, as mentioned above, the Canary Islands are the region with the smallest increase in minimum temperatures, it is the cluster in which TN have increased the most (about one per year). This is due to the existence of higher starting temperatures than in the rest of the country, where, in many cases, the thermal increase is not enough to repeatedly exceed 20°C during the night.

As shown in Figure 12 and summarized in table 3 of the repository, a significant increasing trend, with 99% confidence, is identified in 56 of the 75 stations analysed. In five other observatories, the increasing trend is also statistically significant at a 95% confidence level, while in 11 stations the trend is not significant. The latter, including Salamanca, Ourense, Oviedo or A Coruña, are

observatories whose TN frequency is very occasional, making it difficult to statistically detect trends, similar to the situation in Izaña. To support this argument, in Izaña, for example, during the first 20 years analysed, only three TN were recorded, a figure that rises to 11 in the last 20 years. In Oviedo the three TN of the 1970–1989 period were matched between 2022 (2) and 2023 (1).

On another note, there are generally no notable differences between regions in terms of the intensity of TN, that is, the average thermal intensity of this type of event (Figure 13). The average temperature of TN is 21.7°C in the Southeast, 21.3°C in the Canary Islands, the Inland and the Mediterranean, 21.2°C in the Southwest, 20.9°C in the North Inland and, finally, 20.7°C in the Northwest. There is, roughly speaking, a certain correlation (Pearson correlation coefficient = 0.66), between frequency and intensity; the clusters where the latter is higher are those with a higher annual frequency (the peninsular Southeast and the Canary Islands). However, in third position and with similar results to the Mediterranean and the Southwest, is the Inland, where the annual frequency of TN is much lower. This fact could be due to the different climatic features of

FIGURE 11 Mean annual and decadal frequency, and change rate, of TN (1970–2023).

each of these areas. Thus, while in the Mediterranean and in the south of the country TN are recurrent phenomena, in large areas of the north and inland they still preserve a marked exceptional character linked to very warm episodes, which causes the thermal average to be high, as shown by the exceptionally high values that appear in isolation in these series (Figure 13). Among these inland stations, the observatories of Getafe (21.55°C), Madrid Retiro (21.42°C) and Toledo (21.38°C) stand out.

Regarding the evolution of intensity, 34 stations (45% of the total) show a significant upward trend at 99% confidence, and another six at 95% confidence. On the other hand, only one station with a very low frequency of TN (Zamora) shows a significant decreasing trend in terms of TN intensity. In any case, the Southeast and the Inland are the clusters where, on average, the intensity is increasing the most, while in the Northwest and the North Inland the variations are not very significant.

3.3 | Monthly distribution of TN

The analysis of this parameter shows, once again, the uniqueness of the Canary Islands, while it is the region

where TN are less seasonal. Although it is during the summer months when most TN are concentrated, in the archipelago it is not uncommon for nights of this nature to occur during autumn and the second half of spring (Figure 14). Furthermore, even if they do not represent very high percentages of the total, in many coastal stations it is common to find TN at any time of the year (see table 7 of the repository).

In the rest of the clusters, TN are, according to data from the last five decades, mainly summer phenomena. July and August are the months with the highest frequency, especially in the case of the Inland and the North Inland, where both accumulate more than 70% of the TN for the entire period.

A widening in the TN season is appreciated, so that, comparing the monthly distribution of these between 1970 and 1979 and that of the decade between 2014 and 2023, the months of July and August regress in percentage. Therefore, the latest data indicate that TN tend to be more evenly distributed in all clusters and are no longer concentrated almost exclusively in the summer in some clusters. That is, tropical nights begin to take over in autumn and spring.

FIGURE 12 Rate of change and trends of tropical nights (1970–2023).

FIGURE 13 Intensity of tropical nights (1970–2023).

FIGURE 14 Monthly percentage distribution, and difference between the first and last years of the study, of tropical nights (1970–2023).

3.4 | First and last TN of the year

The analysis of the date on which the first and last tropical night of each year occurs confirms what was mentioned in the previous section. Generally speaking, there is a trend towards an earlier first TN (Figure 15). This is the case, with 99% confidence, in 38 stations (51% of the total), as well as in another 13 (17%) at 90% confidence. On the contrary, no observatory identifies a significant trend consisting of the delay of the first TN. In stations as diverse as Jerez de la Frontera, Segovia, Ourense or Tenerife Norte, the rate of advance is around 1 day per year (table 8 of the repository). The Canary Islands are the region with the earliest occurrence of TN (around May 15). On the other extreme, in the Northwest, the average TN season starts and ends in August.

As for the date on which, on average, the last tropical night of the year occurs, the trends found are significant. Concretely, there is a significant upward trend to 90% in 42 stations, representing almost 56% of the total. In the North Inland and the Inland, the highest rates of delay of this date are identified; for example, the annual rate of change is close to 1 day per year in places such as Badajoz, Valladolid, Hondarribia or Bilbao Airport.

As a result, the TN *season*, that is, the period between the first and the last, has increased considerably. In the Canary Islands, the average is around 6 months (from mid-May to early November), but in recent years it is not unusual to find years with seasons of more than eight or even 10 months. This circumstance does not prevent the rate of advance and delay from being, in general, slower

FIGURE 15 Dates of first and last tropical night by year (1970–2023).

in the archipelago due to the existence of a TN season that, from the outset, was already very long. In any case, all clusters show an extension of this season (Figure 15).

3.5 | Consecutive TN

TN in Spain are becoming more consecutive (Figure 16). The Canary Islands are, by far, the cluster

that averages the most maximum TN per year in the analysed period (48), although the average of the last decade exceeds 70 and in 2023, for the first time, the average exceeded 100 in its observatories. Thus, in stations such as the one located in El Hierro (C929I) or Santa Cruz de Tenerife (C449C), it is common to exceed well over 100 consecutive TN per year, which implies that the population is exposed to high nighttime temperatures for several months with no

FIGURE 16 Frequency of three or more tropical nights per year and annual maximum (1971–2023).

interruption. The data recorded at stations in the Southeast and the Mediterranean are also important, with observatories averaging significant consecutive TN during the summer period; for example, in locations such as Almeria or Valencia in recent years, consecutive TN have been close to 100.

The increase is substantial in the Southwest, as well as in the Inland and the North Inland. In these three cases, although the annual maximum of consecutive TN continues to be modest, there are considerable increases in the number of TN that occur consecutively for at least 3 days. Consequently, in large areas of the country, TN are no longer occurring in isolation, but are increasingly appearing as sequences that affect citizens for several days. In this last indicator, the trends observed in the Canary Islands, which started from high figures at the beginning of the observation period, are very weak and irregular (Figure 16).

3.6 | Relation to relative humidity

The relative humidity (hereinafter RH) is determined by the isolation from the sea, which determines relevant hygrometric differences (Figure 17). Average RH around 70% is identified in different points of the Mediterranean and Atlantic coasts, as well as in the two archipelagos, with the only exception of Izaña. In the Inland, on the other hand, a drier environment prevails and, in addition, the RH during the days when the minimum temperature is above 20°C has different characteristics compared to the coast. While in the Mediterranean, the Canary Islands and some locations on the northern coast, the RH of the TN does not differ too much from normal conditions, in large continental sectors the warm nights are drier in relation to the annual average. Thus, in areas such as Salamanca, Logroño or León, the RH recorded on those days decreases by almost 50%.

FIGURE 17 Annual average of relative humidity by season (1970–2023).

Regarding the evolution of this variable in recent decades, a decreasing trend can be observed in most of the country (Figure 18). In this sense, in 70 stations, a significant decreasing trend is identified with a 99% confidence level. Among the stations that have experienced the greatest rate of decline are Izaña, Puerto de Navacerrada, Córdoba Airport, Cuenca or Huesca Airport, whose average RH has fallen by more than 0.1 points per year.

The analysis of RH trends on days with minimum temperature above 20°C is more complex. As shown in Figure 18, the generalized decline shown above is nuanced when considering only TN. Therefore, in stations such as Cádiz, Jerez de la Frontera, Granada Airport, Oviedo, Lanzarote, Teruel or Donostia, where, on average, RH is decreasing throughout the year, there is an increase in RH during tropical nights. In any case, the trends found are generally less significant on a statistical level than in the previous case. Finally, it is worth mentioning that, in some Mediterranean observatories, a certain trend shift can be distinguished in the last two decades; in places such as Barcelona (Airport), the

decrease in RH on warm nights seems to be minimizing (table 16 of the repository).

4 | DISCUSSION

The results described above show a situation that is quite different from the scenario described by Font-Tullot more than 40 years ago. The author, as mentioned above, pointed then to the Mediterranean region as the area with the highest frequency of TN in the Iberian Peninsula (Font-Tullot, 1983). This being true—without taking into account, obviously, the reality of the Canary Islands—it is clear from the above that, within the Mediterranean coast, it is necessary to differentiate the south-eastern area, where thermal behaviour (at least in terms of minimum temperatures) differs from the rest of the Levantine coast.

It may be stated that, over the last five decades, there has been a generalisation of the frequency of TN in the country. Autonomous communities such as Castilla y

FIGURE 18 Relative humidity trends (1970–2023).

León and Castilla-La Mancha, which used to have very few events, have experienced a substantial increase. An example is the case of the *cluster* corresponding to the inland of the peninsula, whose average number of TN per year has gone from a meagre 4.3 between 1970 and 1979 to over 20 between 2010 and 2019. The northwest region of the peninsula continues to be the area least affected by TN, although there has been a very noticeable increase in recent years. In this regard, between 2020 and 2023, the stations included in this region amounted to 150 TN, a figure that took 21 years to reach from the beginning of the period under analysis.

The characterisation of TN in the different selected locations reveals that the unique environmental conditions of the Canary Islands would encourage a more exhaustive and individualized analysis, especially considering the assiduity of other important phenomena for comfort such as Saharan dust advection (Menéndez et al., 2009). The islands present, in summary, the highest annual frequency of TN, which, in addition, can appear at almost any time of the year and are usually accompanied by a high RH. This reality, which shows that TN is an intrinsic feature of the Canarian climate, explains why

some trends are not entirely significant in the archipelago (see the results related to the evolution of the intensity, how consecutive they are or relative humidity of TN). In other words, the Canary Islands (and, to a lesser extent, the Southeast Iberian Peninsula) have experienced, like the rest of the regions, an important thermal increase at nights, but, unlike the situation in many areas, they started from very high figures in 1970. Hence, it is in the clusters whose series start at lower temperatures that the trends generally show the most significant results. The usefulness of using a threshold index that, in cases such as the Canary Islands, does not reflect the full dimension of the thermal increase observed in the minimum temperatures could be debated, although, in any case, it is valid for making comparisons with other territories, as it has been proven. The speed of environmental changes driven by climate change seems to be calling into question traditional methodologies and indicators that, in certain regions, appear to be insufficient.

In any case, given the universality of the indicator based on TN frequency, studies based on it could be maintained, complementing them with other indexes—for instance, the incidence of other types of nights, such

as equatorial or torrid ($\geq 25^{\circ}\text{C}$), or even those above 30°C . On another note, the environmental contrasts existing within the European continent sometimes lead to certain generalisations about the climate of the different countries that compose it. It is not unusual to find texts and resources in which the Spanish climate is generally classified as *Mediterranean*, *temperate*, *warm* or *subtropical*; it is not in vain that the European Environment Agency rightly places most of the peninsula in the Mediterranean biogeographic region (Cervellini et al., 2020). This type of categorisation is practical for a wide range of purposes, but the impact of phenomena such as TN requires greater analytical precision. This research shows the unequal affection of TN depending on the area of the country (and within each one of them), as well as the different characteristics and trends of these. The results offered by some institutions and authors at an autonomous community scale (NUTS 2) reveal, in most cases, regional averages lower than the existing reality in a large part of the territory (European Environment Agency, n.d.; World Bank, 2021). An example of this are the averages for Catalonia, where the frequency of TN per year ranges from 3.8 in Girona to 61.6 in the Airport of Barcelona.

This generalisation, based on the use of unsuitable scales, as well as the higher frequency observed in highly urbanized environments, refers to the challenges that climate change introduces for cities, especially in relation to urban heat islands, as other studies have already pointed out (Fernández, 2009; Martín-Vide, 2017; Short & Farmer, 2021). This makes the execution of analyses based on data with adequate degrees of resolution advisable for the effective adoption of adaptation measures adjusted to the specificities of each population centre. This need to move towards more detailed analyses is aligned with proposals such as Royé and Martí-Ezpeleta's (2015), who note that the exclusive consideration of the minimum temperature to identify the TN could be insufficient for the purpose of assessing individual comfort, since the thermal evolution of the entire night is not analysed. However, the scarce availability of extensive and quality climatic series with hourly information makes it difficult to carry out more in-depth studies.

On the other hand, several studies in recent years have associated morbidity and mortality with high nighttime temperatures (Christidis et al., 2005; Murage et al., 2017; Royé et al., 2021). This reality is even more relevant in the case of Spain, where, according to the European Environment Agency, the *heat-related mortality incidence* is much higher than in most of the rest of the continent (EEA, 2022). According to the Daily Mortality Monitoring System, associated with the National Epidemiology Centre of the Carlos III Health Institute, between 2015 and 2023 there have been about 37,000

deaths that can be attributed to temperature in Spain (ISCIII, 2024). Results such as the ones presented here are useful for projecting future conditions and seeking effective measures, based on the rates of evolution identified. It seems that, in a few decades, the warmer areas of the country will integrate TN as an inseparable part of their usual nocturnal conditions. The same concern extends to other southern European countries, as evidenced by research addressing the frequency of tropical nights in Italy (Fioravanti et al., 2016), Greece (Georgoulas et al., 2022) or Croatia (Filipčić & Trošić, 2023).

Of particular interest are the results concerning the consecutiveness of TN. The situation in the Southwest, the Inland, the North Inland and the Northwest must be differentiated, where the maximum number of consecutive nights per year is still at relatively low levels, compared to the Canary Islands, the Southeast and the Mediterranean. In these three climatic regions, there are specific spots where minimum temperatures remain uninterruptedly above 20°C for several months. Logically, a warm episode, and in particular a nocturnal one, can be tolerated when it is of an exceptional nature, but it can lead to problems if, as is happening, the anomaly becomes a frequent occurrence in some places.

On the other hand, the relative humidity of the air deserves no less attention. The combination of high temperatures and high humidity can lead to the individual manifesting a feeling of discomfort that is usually referred to among the population as *sultriness* (Guzmán-Hernández et al., 2019). Given the insufficiency of temperature by itself to estimate environmental comfort or wellbeing, several indexes have been developed to measure the degree of dissatisfaction or stress that a person may feel in certain environmental conditions. Some examples of these proposals are the PMV and PPD (Fabbri, 2015), the Humidex (Masitoh & Rusydi, 2020), the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UCTI) (Kuchcik et al., 2021) or the PET (Aquino et al., 2019). All of them include relative humidity as a complementary variable to temperature. As shown in the results, the coastal areas of Spain, where most of the population is concentrated, have very humid TN. According to what has been presented, there is an uncertain evolution of RH during TN in some areas; a decrease is predominant, but some locations near the coast have shown a recent increase in RH during warm nights. In any case, this situation, not applicable to the peninsular territory as a whole, contrasts with the generalized decrease in average humidity throughout the year, a result that coincides with other previously published studies (Mestre et al., 2015; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2014). Authors such as Olcina et al. (2019) find strong evidence of the connection between TN behaviour in the Spanish eastern coast and the

temperature of Mediterranean waters. It should be noted in this regard that, according to authors such as Pastor et al. (2018), the thermal increase that the waters of the western Mediterranean are experiencing is unquestionable, being particularly intense during May, June and July. Thus, there is evidence of an increase in sea surface temperature, at least in the last 40 years, which is estimated to be around 1.3°C (1982–2019) (Pastor et al., 2020). Within the Mediterranean area, in addition to the eastern half, the northernmost part of the western Mediterranean—Gulf of Lion and the Catalan coasts—stands out, where the thermal increase is much higher than the area between the Balearic Islands and the Strait of Gibraltar. The standardized thermal anomalies recorded in the Mediterranean during abnormally warm summers, such as 2022 or 2023, are clearly related to the significant increase in the number of TN in coastal areas (Doğu-Yavaşlı & Erlat, 2024).

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Over the last 50 years, Spain has experienced an increase in its minimum temperatures that generally ranges between 0.03°C and 0.04°C per year, being more intense in the inland areas of the country. This increase translates into an upward trend in the annual frequency of TN, although not homogeneously throughout the country. Thus, the Canary Islands, despite being the Spanish region with the lowest thermal increase in recent decades, have an annual average of TN that is much higher than the rest of the country, at around 100. They are followed by the southeast peninsular and the Mediterranean, with frequencies of around 40 and 60 of this type of nights per year, respectively. Next come, in an intermediate position, the southwest and the inland, with modest figures and usually limited to the summer until a few years ago. Finally, in the northernmost part of the interior and, above all, in the northwest, TN are still sporadic. In any case, except for the stations where TN are very infrequent, there is a very significant increasing trend in the occurrence of these events throughout the country. In the Canary Islands and the Southeast, the increase rate is around 10 TN per decade, a value close to 6 in the case of the Mediterranean, 5 in the Southeast and 4 in the interior.

As for the monthly distribution of these nights, July and August are the months where most of them are concentrated. This is even more accurate in areas of lower annual frequency, where the TN season is largely confined to the summer. In all regions there is a certain

advance of the date on which, on average, the first tropical night of the year appears. In addition, there is a trend towards a delay of the last TN, so that the period in which the population is exposed to high night-time temperatures is clearly increasing.

There are no major differences between regions in terms of TN intensity, although an upward trend can be mentioned at many locations, with varying degrees of statistical significance. In addition, except in the Canary Islands, which started from very high values, and some observatories where TN are very occasional, the frequency of TN occurring at least three nights is increasing. On another note, a generalized decrease in relative humidity is confirmed, with more significant and generalizable trends than RH during TN. In this sense, TN are very humid events in the archipelagos, on the Mediterranean and southern coasts, as well as in many parts of the Cantabrian coast, while they are extraordinarily dry in the inland of the country.

In view of the results obtained, and by way of summary, it can be stated that TN in Spain have shown upward trends in most of the parameters analysed. They are becoming more frequent and intense, distributed over more months of the year, more consecutive, and, in many places, quite wet. We are therefore witnessing a gradual *tropicalisation* of night-time temperatures that is a cause for concern, especially from a health point of view.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Jordan Correa González: Methodology; visualization; data curation; formal analysis; writing – original draft.

Pedro Dorta Antequera: Conceptualization; supervision; project administration; writing – review and editing.

Abel López Díez: Writing – review and editing; methodology; project administration; visualization.

Jaime Díaz Pacheco: Methodology; supervision; data curation; writing – review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in GitHub at https://github.com/resiliex/tropical_nights.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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